

exp(i Action), exp(ipx-iEt) and Fluctuations

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In previous notes (1), we argued that for a free particle, both relativistic and nonrelativistic Lagrangians lead to an $\exp(i \text{ Action})$, which when varied independently in terms of X and T where $\text{velocity} = v = X/T$, lead to the Klein-Gordon and Schrodinger equations respectively. In this note, we argue that: $i d/dT \exp(i \text{ Action}) = E \exp(i \text{ Action})$ and $-i d/dX \exp(i \text{ Action}) = p \exp(i \text{ Action})$ for a free particle. Thus, fluctuations due to the d/dT and d/dX derivatives lead to p and E and so an equation linking these derivatives may be directly related to an energy conservation equation which is already linked in E and p .

Given that d/dT and d/dX acting on $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ lead to E and p , it appears one may obtain other differential equations (i.e. other than the Klein-Gordon one), although one would wish them to be consistent. In particular, one may formulate the Dirac equation as a differential equation (containing d/dT and d/dX as fluctuations), thus allowing a link to the relativistic equation $pp + m^2 = E^2$.

In earlier notes, we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ may be obtained independently of $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ by considering conditional probability $P(p/x)$. Conservation of energy is then imposed to obtain an equation. In the case of a potential $V(x)$, a statistical view is taken as there is a momentum distribution at each x of free particles and $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$. As in the above case, it seems one may not necessarily need to impose conservation of energy in order to create an equation with fluctuations of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$. The Dirac equation is again an example where one has a fluctuation equation linked to $pp + m^2 = E^2$. Thus, for all three cases, the Dirac, Klein-Gordon and Schrodinger equations, one has $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ free particle solutions. For the potential case, one shifts to a momentum distribution linked to $\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $a(p)$ are weights, or the wavefunction.

exp(i Action) and Special Relativity

The action for a relativistic free particle is (2):

$$L = m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2} \quad ((1))$$

It may be shown that by using $v = X/T$ and varying X and T independently:

$$i d/dT \exp(i \text{ Action}) = m_0 / \sqrt{1-v^2} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = E \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$-i d/dX \exp(i \text{ Action}) = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = p \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((2b))$$

To see this more clearly, note that for a free particle:

$$\text{Action} = \int dt L = L(v) T \quad ((3))$$

$$P = dL/dv \quad \text{so } -i \frac{d}{dX} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = \exp(i \text{ Action}) T \frac{dL}{dv} \frac{dv}{dX} \quad \text{where } v = X/T$$

$$= p \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((4a))$$

And

$$H = pv - L \quad \text{together with}$$

$$i \frac{d}{dT} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = \exp(i \text{ Action}) \{ -T \frac{dL}{dT} - L \} = \exp(i \text{ Action}) \{ -T \frac{dL}{dv} \frac{dv}{dT} - L \} \quad \text{where } v = X/T$$

$$\text{so } = \exp(i \text{ Action}) \{ X/T p - L \}$$

$$= \exp(i \text{ Action}) H \quad \text{where } H \text{ is usually energy.} \quad ((4b))$$

For $L = m_0 \sqrt{1 - v^2}$ $H = m_0 / \sqrt{1 - v^2}$ which is energy.

Thus, $i \frac{d}{dT} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = E \exp(i \text{ Action})$ and $-i \frac{d}{dX} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = p \exp(i \text{ Action})$.

Given these relations, one may link d/dT and d/dX fluctuations in an energy conservation equation (which already links E and p). Thus, fluctuation terms $d/dT \exp(i \text{ Action})$ and $d/dX \exp(i \text{ Action})$ become linked with a classical conservation of energy equation. We argue this may be interpreted as a statistical fluctuation picture in which averages match classical values.

(Note: The idea of using $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ initiates with P. Dirac. (3))

Extension to the Dirac Equation

Given that one may link time and spatial fluctuations to E and p , it seems that the most immediate relationship is to use a classical conservation equation, namely energy conservation, and convert it into a differential equation. There may, however, be other relationships, as P. Dirac showed. He was able to write an equation linear in d/dt and d/dx using matrices. The linear equation is consistent with the Klein-Gordon equation. $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ which behaves like $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ under operations of d/dt and d/dx is still a solution. Thus, the underlying oscillatory behaviour of $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ remains for all three equations, the Dirac, Klein-Gordon and Schrodinger. Furthermore, the modulus of this free particle solution is 1.

Statistical Interpretation

We have argued in previous notes that for a free particle behaving in a statistical manner, $P(x) = \text{constant}$, but $P(p/x)$ may not be constant. In fact, we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution such that $d/dx P(p/x) = p P(p/x)$. For the case of potential $V(x)$, we argued that it delivers stochastic hits i.e. $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$, creating a momentum distribution at each x i.e. $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x)$, called the wavefunction, is $\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. In this statistical picture, one may impose conservation of average energy i.e.

$$E = \left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) + V(x) \quad ((5))$$

$W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt) W(x)$ for a bound system. $W(x,t)$ may also be used in the Klein-Gordon and Dirac equations and we argue that it has the same statistical interpretation.

Thus, using $\exp(i \text{Action})$ yields a function whose modulus is 1 and whose id/dt and $-id/dx$ derivatives are $E \exp(i \text{Action})$ and $p \exp(i \text{Action})$ for a free particle. This is a special kind of fluctuation result which follows nicely from the form of Action, although it is possible to suggest the forms $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ without knowledge of $\exp(i \text{Action})$. The fact that E and p appear immediately leads to a differential equation following from a conservation of energy equation. This is consistent with the Action = Integral dt L where the Lagrangian contains the information of the conservation of energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that: $id/dt \exp(i \text{Action}) = E \exp(i \text{Action})$ and $-id/dx \exp(i \text{Action}) = p \exp(i \text{Action})$ for both relativistic ($L = m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$) and nonrelativistic ($L = m_0/2 vv$) cases, where $v=x/t$ and x and t are varied independently. Given this result, one may immediately take a conservation of energy equation (containing E and p) and convert it into a differential equation describing fluctuations. One, however, is not limited to a conservation of energy equation. P. Dirac showed that $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ is also a solution of linear equation in d/dt and d/dx (containing matrices) which is also consistent with the Klein-Gordon equation. Thus, it seems that in quantum mechanics, one establishes fluctuation equations with the idea that $P(p/x) = \exp(ipx)$. We argue that this is a statistical term with modulus 1 and the special property $d/dx P(p/x) = p P(p/x)$. In fact, one may postulate this type of fluctuation without knowing about $\exp(i \text{Action})$ and its properties related to d/dt and d/x (as has been done in previous notes).

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Klein-Gordon Equation, $\exp(i \text{Action})$ [Propagator] and Fluctuations (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Redmount, I. and Suen, W. Path Integration in Relativistic Quantum Mechanics (1992) <https://arxiv.org/abs/gr-qc/9210019v1>
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